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Terrorism or Anti-Apartheid: A Multi-National Overview

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Abstract

International terrorism is a complex phenomenon that involves not just individuals, but multiple states and governments, such as Germany, Israel, and the United States. This article explores the role of international terrorism in perpetuating systemic inequalities, or "apartheid," through military, economic, informational, and even scientific means. It highlights the impact on victims of this international terrorism and advocates for resistance against all forms of apartheid—whether economic, scientific, artistic, political, or legal—as a necessary step towards achieving freedom and justice. The article emphasizes the importance of confronting these multifaceted forms of oppression, particularly when they manifest in extreme economic disparities, such as the exorbitant costs of military actions that disproportionately affect vulnerable populations like Palestinian children.

Keywords: Terrorism, Apartheid

Introduction

The concept of international terrorism extends beyond individual actors to encompass the actions of multiple states and governments that leverage various tools to advance their interests at the expense of others. Countries such as Germany, Israel, and the United States are often cited as examples of state actors involved in what can be termed "international terrorism." This form of terrorism is not limited to violent acts but also includes economic, informational, and even scientific strategies, which foster systemic inequality or apartheid that disproportionately benefits a powerful minority. The misuse of globally accepted "good terms" to justify acts of violence and terrorism, particularly in relation to major constitutional crimes such as those seen in Gaza, has been thoroughly examined (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024a). Notably, these misused terms extend beyond rhetorical manipulation, influencing diplomatic practices and becoming complicit in criminal misconduct by the states involved (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024b).

The Nature of International Terrorism

International terrorism can be understood as a form of violence that is perpetrated not only through physical means but also through economic, informational, and scientific channels. States accused of engaging in international terrorism employ a variety of tools, such as military interventions, economic sanctions, and propaganda campaigns, to further their political agendas. For instance, military interventions in conflict zones, such as Palestine, can be seen as acts of state terrorism that aim to suppress resistance and control resources. The use of such tools often results in a form of international apartheid that segregates and oppresses the weaker sections of society, creating an imbalance that favors the powerful elite.

Struggles Against Apartheid

The struggle for international rights is inherently tied to the battle against apartheid, and vice versa. Those who understand this connection will have a clearer view of the fronts where these battles must be fought. Apartheid, as a system, is not just a structure built upon the earth; it is a concept rooted in a higher, more pervasive

form of injustice. As mentioned in the Quran: "I am better than him; You created me from fire and created him from clay" (Al-A'raf 7:12). This verse highlights the arrogance that often underpins discrimination, a mindset at the core of apartheid. Believing that apartheid is created from "clay" means acknowledging its earthly origins and recognizing that one must rise with the fervor of "fire" to dismantle it.

The comparison between apartheid and fire emphasizes the intensity and commitment required to challenge systems of oppression. Just as fire has the ability to consume and transform, so must the struggle against apartheid aim to eradicate its foundations. Only by adopting such a resolute approach can true justice be achieved on both local and international levels (Mandela, 1994; Said, 1979).

Economic Apartheid as a Tool of Oppression

Economic apartheid refers to the systemic exclusion of certain groups from economic opportunities and resources. This is evident in situations where the cost of a single bomb dropped on Palestinian children exceeds the annual wages of hundreds of people. This stark economic disparity reflects the existence of an economic system that prioritizes military expenditure over the basic needs of people. The international community's failure to address these economic inequalities perpetuates a system of economic apartheid that disproportionately affects vulnerable populations (Chomsky, 2020).

Informational and Scientific Apartheid

Apart from economic apartheid, informational and scientific apartheid are also prevalent in international terrorism. Informational apartheid involves the manipulation and control of media narratives to shape public opinion in favor of the powerful elite. This can be seen in the biased coverage of conflicts where the aggressor is portrayed as the victim and the victim as the aggressor. Similarly, scientific apartheid refers to the use of scientific knowledge and resources to develop advanced weaponry and surveillance technologies that are used to oppress and control populations (Finkelstein, 2018).

Resistance Against All Forms of Apartheid

Resistance against all forms of apartheid—economic, informational, scientific, artistic, political, and legal—is essential to achieving freedom and justice. Those who act against these forms of oppression are often considered freedom fighters. For instance, activists who challenge economic apartheid by advocating for equitable distribution of resources, or who resist informational apartheid by exposing media biases, play a crucial role in the fight for justice. The need for pragmatic action against all forms of apartheid is essential for achieving a just society (Said, 1992).

The Cost of Inaction

The cost of inaction in the face of international terrorism and apartheid is immense. When people fail to act against systemic injustices, they inadvertently contribute to the perpetuation of these systems. The economic cost of military actions, such as the high price of bombs dropped on civilian populations, highlights the urgent need for collective action against these oppressive systems. The struggle for lawful and equitable livelihoods is often met with barriers imposed by economic, military, and legal apartheid, necessitating a collective effort to dismantle these systems (Roy, 2009).

State Terrorism

State terrorism, particularly in the form of economic, psychological, and state-sponsored violence, is often justified under the guise of legality or international resolutions (Chomsky, 2001). In recent days, protests have taken place in Berlin, Hamburg, and other German cities against the government's arms shipments to the volatile Middle East. These protests were met with violent suppression by German military and paramilitary forces, resulting in the deaths of several protestors and the injury or deportation of others. The German government, however, has consistently placed the blame on Islamist groups, deflecting responsibility for the unrest (Klein, 2023).

Germany, with its historical record of state violence and radicalism, has again shifted towards ideological racism, this time under the guise of anti-Semitic-Arab policies. This new wave of racism, while echoing historical prejudices, now operates through a Zionist lens, as modern racism is shaped by ideologies that trace back to Herzl and the roots of Zionism (Pappe, 2017). The psychological, economic, and security well-being of populations in distant regions is once again under attack, driven by ideological forces emanating from Germany's foreign policies.

Further complicating the issue, some German military and paramilitary personnel have reportedly been involved with the Israeli Defense Forces (IDF) or have contributed in advisory roles, offering training to individuals linked to Zionist international crimes (Finkelstein, 2003). This reflects the growing role of Germany in supporting state-sponsored terrorism, often justified by legal frameworks but resulting in widespread violence and oppression, especially in the context of the Middle East.

Conclusion

International terrorism is not limited to the actions of rogue individuals or groups; it is a systemic issue involving multiple states and governments. The use of military, economic, informational, and scientific tools to create a favorable environment for a powerful minority is a form of international terrorism that perpetuates various forms of apartheid. To combat these forms of oppression, it is crucial to recognize and resist them in all their manifestations. Only through concerted efforts against economic, informational, scientific, and other forms of apartheid can a more just and equitable world be achieved.

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